

7th German Human Factors Summer
School

Program & Abstractband

October 8th - 9th, 2025

Organizers:

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Part I

General Information

Welcome

We are happy to welcome you all to the Seventh German Human Factors Summer School 2025. The German Summer School for Human Factors is the successor of the Berlin Summer School of Human Factors which was initiated and organized from 2014-2018 by the Department of Psychology and Ergonomics, TU Berlin. The Summer School is an annual postgraduate event that is supported by the Section of Engineering Psychology of the German Psychological Society (DGPs).

The intention is to provide an interactive platform that promotes the transfer and communication of interdisciplinary skills relevant to Human Factors research. Successful postgraduate applicants (Ph.D., M.Sc., and candidates) have the opportunity to present their research interests and/or current projects for critical discussion. Prominent researchers are invited to teach advanced methods and communicate state-of-the-art research from their laboratories.

The 7th German Summer School for Human Factors is hosted by Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz from October 8th to 9th. We are looking forward to inspiring talks and discussions.

Target audience

The target audience is Ph.D. students working in Human Factors, irrespective of whether they have just started or almost finished their Ph.D. The objective of the Summer School of Human Factors is to offer a space for Ph.D. students to connect and help each other with the empirical parts and handling of other issues concerning the Ph.D. Also, the summer school will be attended by invited senior researchers and guests, further facilitating the discussions.

Venue

The summer school will take place at Binger Straße 14–16 (Psychologisches Institut, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz). The Venue can easily be reached by public transport or car.

Information for presenters

Each talk will be scheduled for 30 or 60 minutes (depending on whether it is a short or long discussion format:

- During the talk, contributors can give a short introduction to their current project (8-10 mins.) and afterwards the contributor has the opportunity to freely design a workshop format to address key issues with the audience, e.g. initialize and lead a discussion with the audience or group assignments. For the workshop format, notes, pens, etc. will be provided facilitating the creative process. We want to establish a convenient atmosphere for the speaker and a lively exchange of ideas later on.
- A long discussion will be scheduled for 60 minutes: Introduction (8-10 mins) and workshop (40 mins).
- A short discussion will be scheduled for 30 minutes: Introduction (8-10 mins) and workshop (20 mins).

All posters will be presented in a poster session (60 mins). The audience will have the opportunity to ask questions and discuss the different topics.

Questions?

If you want to get in touch with the organizers to discuss some ideas or upcoming questions, please get in touch via email:

- HFSS2025@uni-mainz.de

Program

Wednesday, 08.10.2025

08:30 – 09:00 Registration and Coffee

09:00 – 09:30 **Welcome**

9:30 – 10:30 **Meaningful Work In the Age of AI: The Role of
Technology Agency in the Experience of Meaning
and Responsibility at Work**

Mara Hofbauer

10:30 – 11:30 **Source memory for AI-vs. human-generated online
content**

Luise Metzger

11:30 – 12:30 **In-Vehicle UX in Performance Vehicles:
An Experience- and Need-Oriented HMI Design
Approach for Enhancing Positive Emotional States**

Eileen Merstorf

12:30 – 13:30 **Lunch Break**

13:30 – 14:30 **Posters and Coffee**

14:30 – 15:30 **Executive Functions as Multidimensional Drivers of
Human Adaptation to Emerging Technologies: A
Theoretical Synthesis and Revised Taxonomy**

Eva Gößwein

15:30 – 16:00 **Automatisierung im Führerstand - Job Design
als Akzeptanzfaktor für GoA3+**

Gina Schnücker

16:00 – 16:30 **Coffee Break**

16:30 – 17:30 **Unlocking Transparency: Open Science Practices for
Data Preparation**

Hanna Schindler

from 19:00 **Dinner at “Beim Budiker“**

Address: Raimundstraße 13, Mainz

Thursday, 09.10.2025

09:00 – 09:30 **Coffee**

9:30 – 9:45 **What Is Science Communication? - And Why It Matters**
Selina Beckmann

9:45 – 10:00 **Human & Machine: Science Communication in Teaching**
Marlene Wessels

10:00 – 12:00 **Science Communication Workshop**
Selina Beckmann & Marlene Wessels

12:00 – 13:00 **Lunch Break**

13:00 – 13:30 **Interaction Space for the Teleoperation of Tram Trains**
Alexandra Nick

13:30 – 14:00 **When the Human Factor is Needed: Psychological
Mechanisms in Supervisory Control and Automation
in High-Risk Work Enviroments**
Maike Ramrath

14:00 – 14:30 **Energy-optimized headlamp distribution in urban areas**
Alina Waldmann

14:30 – 15:00 **Concluding Session**

15:00 – 15:30 **Coffee Break and Conclusion**

Presentation topics overview

Mara Hofbauer	Ludwig-Maximilians- Universität München	Long Discussion	Meaningful Work In the Age of AI: The Role of Technology Agency in the Experience of Meaning and Responsibility at Work
Luise Metzger	University Mannheim	of Long Discussion	Source memory for AI-vs. human-generated online content
Eileen Merstorf	Mercedes-AMG GmbH	Long Discussion	In-Vehicle UX in Performance Vehicles: An Experience- and Need-Oriented HMI Design Approach for Enhancing Positive Emotional States
Markus Amann	Honda Research Institute Europe GmbH	Poster	Coordinating Internal and External HMIs for Cooperative Driver-Pedestrian Situation Resolution
Tim Kreitmaier	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaft Landshut	Poster	Entwicklung eines digitalen Trainingsprogramms für Menschen mit Schwerhörigkeit
Maike Lindermayr	Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz	Poster	Designed to Feel Human? A Within-Subjects Study on the Influence of Anthropomorphic Design Cues on the Perception of AI-Driven Chatbots

Melika Miralem	University of Bergen	Poster	The Illusion of Absence: Perceptual Consequences in Controlled and Driving Contexts
Tim Niewalda	Johannes Gutenberg- Universität Mainz	Poster	Mechanisms of Anxiety in Human-Robot Interactions: An affective information processing approach
Insa Schaffernak	Technische Hochschule Augs- burg	Poster	Artificial Intelligence in Ophthalmology: How Hybrid Decision-Making Can Succeed
Nellie Zienert	Otto-Friedrich- Universität Bamberg, Industrieanlagen- Betriebsgesellschaft mbH	Poster	When the Unexpected Occurs: The Influence of Human-Machine Interaction on User Reactions in Automated Vehicles
Elisabeth Wöger- bauer	Johannes Gutenberg- Universität Mainz	Poster	How sound properties affect preferred distances in human-drone interaction
Niklas Grünewald	Johannes Gutenberg- Universität Mainz	Poster	Giving Robots a Hard Time: A Field Experiment on the Role of Robots' Social Behavior and Social Norms for Robot Bullying

Eva Gößwein	University of Duisburg-Essen	Long Discussion	Executive Functions as Multidimensional Drivers of Human Adaptation to Emerging Technologies: A Theoretical Synthesis and Revised Taxonomy
Gina Schnücker	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.	Short Discussion	Automatisierung im Führerstand - Job Design als Akzeptanzfaktor für GoA3+
Hanna Schindler	Technische Universität Berlin	Long Discussion	Unlocking Transparency: Open Science Practices for Data Preparation
Alexandra Nick	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	Short Discussion	Interaction Space for the Teleoperation of Tram Trains
Maike Ramrath	University of Wuppertal	Short Discussion	When the Human Factor is Needed: Psychological Mechanisms in Supervisory Control and Automation in High-Risk Work Environments
Alina Waldmann	L-LAB, Forviva Hella	Short Discussion	Energy-optimized headlamp distribution in urban areas

Part II

Abstracts

Coordinating Internal and External HMIs for Cooperative Driver-Pedestrian Situation Resolution

Markus Amann, Thomas H. Weisswange, Malte Probst,
Stina Larsson, Maytheewat Aramrattana, Anna Sjörs
Dahlman, Miguel Ángel Sotelo

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Traffic interactions between vehicles and pedestrians are inherently uncertain due to the dynamic nature of the interaction partners' behavior and situational ambiguity. The exchange of information between drivers and other road users could improve mutual understanding of the situation and planned behavior. Existing products and research approaches aim at enhancing mutual understanding by providing information through internal or external human-machine interfaces (HMIs). To foster mutual understanding and a joint resolution, it is necessary to combine both types of HMIs and provide reasoning mechanisms to coordinate them. We propose a cooperative HMI (cHMI) system that coordinates traffic interactions by communicating behavioral recommendations both to the driver of a car and to outside road users. The system analyzes the current traffic situation, calculates potential cooperative behavior options, derives behavior recommendations for each partner, and harmonizes external HMI (eHMI) and internal HMI (iHMI) signals to improve the safety and reduce ambiguity of a cooperative traffic situation. It effectively synchronizes driver data and sensor data from other road users to enable an optimal joint action between the interaction partners. With this, the cHMI facilitates that all road users share the same understanding of how the situation should proceed, ensuring a safe interaction. We evaluate the system through user experiments with 70 participants in a multiplayer Virtual Reality (VR) simulation environment where pedestrians and drivers can safely interact in the

same experiment. We tested interactions in uncertain situations with cars approaching pedestrians at unsignalized and unmarked road crossings. Results show a significant increase of cooperative interactions resolved by the pedestrian crossing in front of the vehicle. Drivers show stronger and earlier yielding cues which allow the pedestrians to initiate the crossing significantly faster compared to interactions without the system. The joint resolution time (JRT) until both traffic participants pass through the interaction does not change significantly with the cHMI.

Executive Functions as Multidimensional Drivers of Human Adaptation to Emerging Technologies: A Theoretical Synthesis and Revised Taxonomy

Eva Gößwein

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This contribution explores the foundations of human adaptation, focusing on adaptive performance as a critical construct for understanding how individuals navigate change in the context of emerging technologies. Drawing on seminal theories such as the I-ADAPT model (Ployhart & Bliese, 2006), the taxonomy of adaptive performance (Pulakos et al., 2000), and the multilevel conceptual architecture of adaptation (Baard et al., 2014), the work synthesizes key insights into the interplay between individual differences, cognitive mechanisms, and performance outcomes. A revised taxonomy of adaptation is proposed, structured around three dimensions: (1) individual differences (e.g., trait adaptability, cognitive abilities), (2) mechanisms of adaptive performance (e.g., goal setting, knowledge development, trust in technology), and (3) adaptive performance change (e.g., transition and reacquisition adaptation). The framework emphasizes the role of cognitive functions - such as working memory, inhibitory control, and cognitive flexibility - as predictors of adaptive performance, aligning with the focus of this PhD project on executive functions. By contextualizing adaptation within human technology interactions (e.g., driving simulators, robots), the contribution bridges theoretical models with empirical applications, highlighting how mechanisms like technology acceptance and experience mediate adaptation processes. The revised taxonomy not only advances theoretical coherence in adaptation research but also provides a structured lens for investigating how humans dynamically adjust to

technological change. This aims to stimulate the discussion on cognitive and behavioral underpinnings of adaptation, which forms the second part of this contribution. In this discussion, participant will have the chance to integrate the proposed framework with their own work, further challenging and enhancing its empirical foundation and interconnectedness.

Giving Robots a Hard Time: A Field Experiment on the Role of Robots' Social Behavior and Social Norms for Robot Bullying

Johannes Kraus, Niklas Grünewald, Charlotte Kapell,
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Robot bullying, defined as purposeful obstructive or harmful behavior toward robots that impedes their tasks, is a widely discussed but still little researched phenomenon. Research findings under realistic conditions are somewhat contradictory (Bartneck & Keijsers, 2020; Raab et al., 2025; Yamada et al., 2023) and contributing factors have not been sufficiently investigated. In this field experiment ($N = 35$), we investigated how social norms of robot bullying and social role behavior of robots affect bullying of a cleaning robot. Social norm (pro bullying vs. anti bullying) and the social role behavior (cooperative-polite vs. functional-technological (impolite)) were experimentally manipulated. Bullying was operationalized by an adaptation of the hot sauce paradigm (Lieberman et al., 1999), in which participants chose the amount of soiling liquid to be poured onto the robot's cleaning area. In addition, trust, anthropomorphism, safety and perceived intelligence were assessed. Results showed a significantly higher tendency for bullying towards the impolite robot than the polite one. The social norm of robot bullying and the interaction between independent variables did not show a significant effect. Trust, perceived intelligence and anthropomorphism, but not safety, were higher for the polite than the impolite robot. These findings suggest that robots' social roles affect how humans perceive and treat them - e.g. show harmful behaviors - whereas social norms, in this context, may offer limited leverage.

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Meaningful Work In the Age of AI: The Role of Technology Agency in the Experience of Meaning and Responsibility at Work

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Technology has been a common factor in the workplace for decades, but recent developments in artificial intelligence (AI) are changing our relation to workplace technology (Singla et al., 2025). AI is more agentic than previous technologies, meaning that it can act increasingly proactive, autonomous, and self-governed (O’Neill et al., 2022).

Potential risks of interacting with highly agentic technology, like AI, in the workplace are a loss of responsibility (Sadeghian et al., 2024), and a loss of meaning at work (Kobiella et al., 2024). Feeling responsible for a task outcome and experiencing meaning at work are preconditions for work motivation (Hackman & Oldham, 1976) and are associated with wellbeing, commitment, and decreased turnover intentions (Allan et al., 2019). Thus, it is necessary to understand whether increasingly agentic technologies are diminishing the experience of responsibility and meaning at work. While some studies investigated the effect of technology agency in tasks like smart heating (Christoforakos et al., 2024), vacuum cleaning (Diefenbach et al., 2024), or text production (Draxler et al., 2024), our understanding of the effects of agency on the experience of meaningful work is limited.

Therefore, we are conducting a number of qualitative and quantitative studies to first understand the experience of meaning in modern workplaces, and then test how technology agency affects these meaningful experiences. This

project is linking theories of meaningful work (Lips-Wiersma & Wright, 2012) to self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000, 2017) and Weiner's theory of social cognition (Weiner, 1995), to give a comprehensive understanding of the effect of technology agency on the experience of work. Our goal is to work towards a sweet spot of technology agency, which supports people in their task fulfillment without potentially limiting the experience of meaning and responsibility at work.

Description of Goal of the Discussion: The goal of the discussion is to first identify work tasks that hold meaning for a person, and second, to explore how technology agency could be operationalized for these tasks in experimental studies. Especially, how technology could appear more or less agentic to a person in the automation of these tasks. The results of this discussion will inform the experimental studies I plan to conduct for my PhD.

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Entwicklung eines digitalen Trainingsprogramms für Menschen mit Schwerhörigkeit

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Schwerhörigkeit zählt zu den häufigsten chronischen Erkrankungen im Erwachsenenalter. Dennoch bleiben viele Betroffene unterversorgt, was zu erheblichen Einschränkungen im alltäglichen Leben führen kann. Während es im deutschsprachigen Raum bereits einige digitale Anwendungen zum Umgang mit der Schwerhörigkeit gibt, fehlen konkrete Trainingsangebote, die eigenständig und alltagsnah von Betroffenen durchgeführt werden können.

Das Projekt HörTrain verfolgt das Ziel, ein digitales Trainingsprogramm zur Unterstützung für Menschen mit Schwerhörigkeit zu entwickeln. Betroffene sollen dabei Anpassungsstrategien erlernen, die in den Alltag integriert werden können und zur Steigerung der Lebensqualität beitragen sollen. Das Trainingskonzept für HörTrain wurde zusammen mit Fachpersonen aus der Audiologie, der Hörakustik und der psychosozialen Beratung erarbeitet. Dabei wurden neben den Grundlagen für das didaktische Konzept auch erste Anforderungen an die technische Entwicklung erhoben.

Die Entwicklung der Anwendung erfolgt in Anlehnung an den nutzerzentrierten Gestaltungsprozess (DIN EN ISO 9241-210 2020) als mobile App. Bereits durchgeführt wurden die Entwicklung einer Informationsarchitektur und die systematische Erstellung von vier Personas, die typische Nutzergruppen im Kontext der Schwerhörigkeit abbilden. Sie unterscheiden sich unter

anderem hinsichtlich der Technikaffinität, des Versorgungsstatus und der Motivation für Veränderungen. Die Personas dienen aktuell als zentrale Referenzpunkte für die inhaltliche Strukturierung und gestalterische Ausrichtung der App. Sowohl Fachpersonen als auch Nutzer werden stets in den weiteren Entwicklungsprozess eingebunden, um die Gebrauchstauglichkeit und die Relevanz der App sicherzustellen.

Das Projekt befindet sich somit aktuell an der Schnittstelle zwischen Konzeption und Entwicklung. Im Fokus stehen dabei Fragen der Interaktionsgestaltung, der modularen Strukturierung von Inhalten und der Konkretisierung der funktionalen Anforderungen an das Trainingsprogramm. Parallel dazu wird die anstehende Evaluation vorbereitet, die nach der Implementierungsphase durchgeführt werden soll.

Ergänzend zu diesen Themen ist ein systematisches Review zu digitalen Gesundheitsapplikationen geplant. Ziel dabei ist es, bestehende Interaktionsdesigns zu analysieren und daraus Gestaltungsmuster für die Entwicklung der App abzuleiten.

Designed to Feel Human? A Within-Subjects Study on the Influence of Anthropomorphic Design Cues on the Perception of AI-Driven Chatbots

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Recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI), particularly in machine learning and natural language processing (NLP), have led to the emergence of generative chatbots that increasingly imitate human communication patterns by employing anthropomorphic design cues such as names, profile pictures, diverse communicative styles, and simulated typing behavior. Although prior studies have highlighted the persuasive potential of such technologies (Costello et al., 2024; Salvi et al., 2025), empirical evidence on the effects of anthropomorphic design cues in human-chatbot interaction remains limited. The present study addresses this gap through a within-subjects online experiment with a representative German sample ($N = 221$), systematically examining how anthropomorphic design cues in chatbot interfaces and dialogue styles shape user perception. Across twelve chatbot interfaces, anthropomorphic cues in the dimensions of identity, verbal, and nonverbal cues (Seeger et al., 2021) were experimentally manipulated, both in isolation and in combination, and evaluated by participants with respect to perceived anthropomorphism, trust, reliability, competence, intention to use, uncanniness, and anxiety. In addition, dispositional variables - including the Tendency to Anthropomorphize Technology (ANTEN), Propensity to Trust in Automated Technology (PTT-A), AI literacy, and general attitudes toward AI - were assessed. The findings indicate that dispositional variables, particularly ANTEN, exert a stronger influence on anthropomorphic perception than experimental manipulations of interface

design. The latter primarily enhanced anthropomorphic perception among individuals with low ANTEN. To intentionally foster perceived human-likeness through chatbot interface design, a combined use of multiple anthropomorphic cues - particularly verbal cues in combination with other cue categories - appears most effective, provided that individual dispositional differences are taken into account. Furthermore, anthropomorphism was moderately positively associated with trust ($b = .40$, $SE = .04$) and weakly negatively associated with uncanniness ($b = -.16$, $SE = .04$). Reliability and competence emerged as the strongest predictors of trust and partially mediated the relationship between anthropomorphism and trust. Nonetheless, these findings represent only an initial step, underscoring the need for integrative theoretical frameworks and dynamic, interaction-oriented approaches to capture the multifaceted nature of human-chatbot interaction.

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In-Vehicle UX in Performance Vehicles: An Experience- and Need-Oriented HMI Design Approach for Enhancing Positive Emotional States

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Despite the increasing relevance of experience- and need-oriented approaches in user experience (UX) research, their application to the specific context of performance vehicles remains limited. For performance manufacturers, emotionalisation plays a crucial role in conveying brand identity and addressing the needs of the target group. This segment thus facilitates the empirical investigation of positive affective user responses, providing an accessible and insightful context representative of the broader automotive market. Due to their inherent abstraction, it is challenging to meaningfully integrate psychological needs into design processes without the aid of sophisticated methodological frameworks (Zeiner et al., 2016). This causes a discrepancy between theoretical understanding and practical applicability in human-machine interaction (HMI) design. The PhD project aims to address the aforementioned gap by developing practice-oriented design aspects that render implicit psychological needs tangible and applicable for HMI design in performance vehicles (Krueger & Brandenburg, 2024). To this end, a mixed-methods approach is employed and structured into three research strands.

The first research strand focuses on the systematic exploration of relevant experience categories in the context of performance vehicles (Zeiner et al.,

2018). This will be achieved by experience interviews with performance drivers, supported by emotion cards based on Desmet's (2012) 25 product emotions. In the second strand, these experience categories are translated into concrete usage scenarios (Haspel et al., 2022). An online study with performance drivers follows, employing a standardised needs questionnaire (Huang et al., 2025) to assess the relevance of psychological needs within each scenario. The resulting data are used to identify statistically grounded need-experience clusters. The third strand focuses on the development and validation of HMI design aspects that can intentionally evoke the targeted positive emotional states. Creative workshops are utilised to progressively evolve emotional HMI concepts that are tailored to the identified experience categories and psychological needs. These concepts are then implemented as prototypes and evaluated in usability labs using valence analysis, laddering techniques, and emotion scales.

This thesis makes a significant contribution to UX research by integrating psychological models, emotion-driven design, and technological innovations, thus bridging the gap between design practice and scientific research in an applied field in order to foster sustainable positive UX in performance vehicles.

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Source memory for AI- vs. human-generated online content

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The increased capabilities and availability of large language models have changed the online information landscape: Apart from traditional, human-curated sources - such as forums, news websites, or encyclopedias -, AI-generated information - such as chatbot responses or automated search summaries - is now also readily available. This research project examines whether people spontaneously categorize and recall web content as human- vs. AI-generated.

In an initial online study ($N = 101$), we adapted the "Who said what?" paradigm (Klauer & Wegener, 1998; Taylor et al., 1978): Participants were shown 84 trivia statements randomly allocated to one of six websites, three of which were human- and three AI-generated. After a filler task, they then completed a source monitoring test where they were presented with the original 84 statements along with 42 new statements and were asked for each if it was new, or, if they assumed they had seen it previously, which website it had appeared on. We further assessed individual attitude measures: Given previous findings that skepticism about a source's credibility is associated with increased source monitoring (Pena et al., 2017), we expected negative attitudes towards AI to enhance participants' monitoring of AI-generated sources.

We analyzed the data using hierarchical multinomial processing trees with hierarchical ML estimation (Nestler & Erdfelder, 2023) based on Klauer and Wegener's (1998) two-high-threshold model of social categorization. Results indicate that categorization occurs only partially: While human-generated

websites are recalled as such, AI-generatedness of a website was not recalled.

Thus, AI source monitoring could also not be correlated with attitude measures. However, website-specific memory in this initial study was poor, which could indicate that insufficient attention was paid to the sources and categorization could not be observed accordingly.

To address this, we are currently planning a follow-up study implementing stronger experimental controls and design features aimed at directing participants' attention more explicitly to the source of the information.

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The Illusion of Absence: Perceptual Consequences in Controlled and Driving Contexts

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The illusion of absence refers to a perceptual phenomenon where the space behind an occluder is experienced as empty, despite insufficient visual information to support such a conclusion. This illusion has implications for both basic vision science and real world safety, particularly in driving contexts. In a controlled laboratory study, we tested predictions from the generic view principle, which suggests that narrower occluders should amplify the illusion. Using perceived levitation of physical objects as a proxy for perception of space as empty, we found that narrower obstructions indeed increased the illusion of absence, and that monocular viewing reduced the effect - likely due to diminished depth cues. These findings contribute to the ongoing debate on the role of seeing versus knowledge in visual experiences.

Extending this research to a driving context, we investigated whether car A-pillars - structural components known to create blind zones - also evoke the illusion of absence. In a virtual reality simulation, participants viewed a traffic scenario in which a hidden car emerged from behind the A-pillar, resulting in a near-collision. Preliminary data from 55 participants revealed high levels of surprise, particularly with narrower A-pillars, suggesting that the illusion of absence may reinforce the belief that nothing is hidden behind them. These results highlight the potential safety risks posed by perceptual illusions in driving environments. By identifying the conditions that amplify this illusion, we aim to inform future applications in virtual reality, perceptual training, and automotive design to mitigate its potentially detrimental effects.

Interaction Space for the Teleoperation of Tram Trains

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Teleoperation is a fallback solution for highly automated tram systems operating in mixed traffic. Thereby, the highly automated tram alerts the teleoperator in problematic or insecure cases. These cases include monitoring and giving clearance around stations, interacting with passengers, communicating with external agents such as other vehicles, pedestrians, cyclists, traffic controllers, or emergency services, and infrastructure manipulation (e.g., changing switches). With this understanding of teleoperation, we are no longer talking about continuous monitoring but about switching contexts and reacting to alerts within a limited (so far undefined) time frame. This is closely related to a potential shift that challenges attention allocation and situational understanding. Thereby, teleoperation leads to new workplace demands and an extended understanding of information processing, considering underload, overload, and responsibility.

This discussion explores interaction requirements and control options for teleoperators in different categories of tram operation scenarios. In a 20-minute small-group discussion, each group analyzed one of four cases: (1) operation between two cities, (2) situations around stations (± 1 minute), (3) interaction with passengers, and (4) interaction with other road users. For each case, participants identified a representative task and discussed the associated requirements for teleoperator actions, such as braking, accelerating, granting clearance, or communicating with passengers and external actors.

The discussion results were consolidated in a plenary session. The key outcomes indicate that interaction with passengers is mainly relevant in exceptional situations (e.g., unexpected delays or accidents) and can otherwise

be automated, similar to existing train systems. A simple "alarm" or "contact teleoperator" button was considered sufficient for passenger-initiated communication. Participants emphasized the need for multiple camera views covering the track, its surrounding and the vehicle cabin. Predictive computing (e.g., hazard probability estimation in shared spaces, heat maps) is considered as useful to guide teleoperators' attention. Furthermore, reliable voice communication and quick access to field teams were deemed essential, alongside options to communicate with external persons near the tram (e.g., truck drivers blocking shared lanes).

Overall, the discussion highlights concrete design implications for teleoperator workplaces, underscoring their potential to enhance safety and operational efficiency in public transport while addressing workforce shortages.

Mechanisms of Anxiety in Human-Robot Interactions: An affective information processing approach

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Emotional states are increasingly acknowledged as an important factor in human-robot interaction (HRI) and in the formation and calibration of adjacent psychological constructs, such as trust, regarded as a prerequisite for appropriate system use. However, the specific impact of situationally experienced anxiety on trust calibration during HRI remains under-explored.

Building upon a recently developed questionnaire to assess *Specific Robot Anxiety* (SRA), this poster presents two interrelated research paths. The first focuses on the iterative refinement and validation of the SRA measure. On this basis, the second path explores anxiety's dynamic influence on trust calibration processes, paying particular attention to how situational affect modulates the processing of system- and context-related cues used to evaluate a robot's trustworthiness.

The poster presents preliminary ideas and an open research agenda, inviting discussion on methodological approaches, experimental designs and theoretical perspectives for exploring how affective states influence trust calibration in HRI.

When the Human Factor is Needed: Psychological Mechanisms in Supervisory Control and Automation in High-Risk Work Environments

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In high-risk work domains such as air traffic control, crisis management, and industries with hazardous processes, advancing automation is fundamentally reshaping the role of human operators. Increasingly, humans are transitioning from hands-on controllers to supervisory monitors, overseeing automated processes and intervening primarily in response to rare but critical system events such as warnings, errors, or failure alerts.

These infrequent yet high-stakes interventions place significant demands on operators' cognitive resources. While the structural impacts of automation and supervisory control have been widely examined, the psychological processes underlying human responses to critical system information remain underexplored.

The present dissertation aims to address this research gap by systematically investigating how professionals in safety-critical environments cognitively and emotionally process system-related critical information. The project focuses on key psychological factors, including trust, user experience, and mental workload. A multi-method approach will be employed, consisting of four studies: (1) a systematic literature review synthesizing current knowledge on the psychological effects of system-critical messages, (2) a qualitative study exploring the role of trust through practitioner interviews, paired with an online validation study, (3) a quantitative experiment examining the perception and interpretation of system errors and (4) a quantitative study on trust repair

mechanisms following technological failures.

The anticipated contribution of this dissertation is twofold: Theoretically, it will enhance our understanding of the psychological mechanisms guiding human interactions with automated systems in high-risk settings. Practically, it will generate evidence-based recommendations for the design of socio-technical systems that foster appropriate trust calibration, reduce mental workload, and support effective human intervention during critical events. These findings aim to facilitate safer and more resilient processes in increasingly automated, high-risk work environments.

Artificial Intelligence in Ophthalmology: How Hybrid Decision-Making Can Succeed

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The use of artificial intelligence (AI) as a decision-support system in medicine holds the potential to increase diagnostic accuracy and reduce the workload of medical professionals. But how should such systems be designed and integrated into clinical practice so that they are accepted by both physicians and patients? In my doctoral project, I examine how hybrid decision-making processes (i.e., situations in which physicians receive support from AI systems in making medical decisions) can succeed in ophthalmology, taking into account psychological processes and topics related to human-machine interaction. To this end, two studies were conducted.

In our interview study with ophthalmologists, it became clear that openness toward medical AI systems alone is not sufficient for their long-term integration into everyday clinical practice. Rather, a variety of factors plays a role, such as characteristics of the AI system, institutional infrastructure, adopter characteristics, and patient acceptance. Moreover, what appeared to distinguish AI systems from traditional, digital tools was the ophthalmologists' psychological appraisal of these systems.

In a second, experimental mixed-methods study, we investigated the perspective of individuals affected by AI-supported medical decisions ("decision subjects"). The aim of the experimental vignette study was to capture reactions to diagnostic decisions that involved AI in different ways. The results show that the type of AI involvement influences potential patients' trust in the

final medical decision. Both the type of AI support as well as its supposed integration into the physician's decision-making workflow affected reported trust in the medical decision. Results from sentiment analysis and qualitative coding of open-ended responses further highlight the differing perceptions of various configurations of human-AI decision-making in medical contexts, and provide suggestions for integrating AI decision support into medical consultations that do not diminish, but ideally increase trust in the medical decisions.

Unlocking Transparency: Open Science Practices for Data Preparation

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Open science practices - such as preregistering hypotheses and analysis strategies or publishing datasets - are increasingly applied in the field of psychophysiology. Research in this area often follows a confirmatory approach, with clearly defined (and increasingly preregistered) hypotheses and statistical analysis plans. However, the data structures involved are typically complex and require extensive preprocessing before hypothesis testing can be performed. These preprocessing steps cannot always be fully anticipated and often depend on data quality or other unforeseen characteristics of the dataset. As a result, complete preprocessing pipelines are rarely preregistered. This is concerning given that preprocessing introduces a high degree of analytical flexibility, which can drastically impact study outcomes.

In my input presentation, I will illustrate this issue using the example of my first Ph.D. study, which was a confirmatory psychophysiology study with preregistered hypotheses and statistical analysis plans (<https://osf.io/8q9gm>), but without a preregistered preprocessing plan. The goal of the study was to identify psychophysiological markers that can reflect changes in mental workload. We used the Multi-Attribute Task Battery - a dynamic multitasking environment simulating aviation-related tasks - to systematically induce different levels of workload. Among other measures, we recorded eye-tracking data using a video-based remote system that outputs fully accessible raw gaze data.

The transformation of raw gaze coordinates into gaze metrics - such as fixations or saccades - involves multiple decisions regarding filtering, artifact rejection, and data segmentation. We applied several published and peer-reviewed

preprocessing pipelines to the data and found that the resulting gaze metrics varied considerably depending on the pipeline used. This observation raises two key questions: (1) What strategy should guide the selection of a preprocessing pipeline, especially when multiple valid options exist? And (2) how can such rather exploratory preprocessing decisions be transparently reported in a way that aligns with open science principles - without undermining the credibility of an otherwise confirmatory study?

Automatisierung im Führerstand - Job Design als Akzeptanzfaktor für GoA3+

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Um den schienengebundenen Verkehr in Zukunft sicherer, effizienter und kostengünstiger zu gestalten, werden derzeit verschiedene Konzepte für höhere Automatisierungsstufen (Grades of Automation, GoA) im Bahnbereich diskutiert. Für GoA3 ist vorgesehen, dass Triebfahrzeugführende (Tf) das Fahrzeug nicht mehr direkt vor Ort steuern, sondern die Automated Train Operation (ATO) im Störfall als sogenannte Remote Train Operator (RTO) überwachen und im Notfall eingreifen.

Diese Konzepte verändern die Tätigkeiten der Tf grundlegend und werfen sowohl arbeits- als auch ingenieurspsychologische Fragestellungen auf. Aspekte wie Performanz, Müdigkeit, Situationsbewusstsein und Belastung wurden daher in der Vergangenheit bereits untersucht. Obwohl die Akzeptanz der Tf gegenüber ATO als einer der grundlegendsten Faktoren für eine erfolgreiche Migration hin zu GoA3 betrachtet wird, bleibt dieser Aspekt in der Human Factors Forschung weitgehend unbeachtet. In dieser Arbeit wird daher untersucht, inwiefern die Einführung von GoA3 Aspekte der Arbeitsqualität von Triebfahrzeugführenden berührt und ob eine potenzielle Veränderung dieser Aspekte einen Einfluss auf die Akzeptanz gegenüber GoA3 durch die Tf hat. Hierfür wurden 66 Tf in einer Online-Vignettenstudie hinsichtlich ihres Erlebens von Veränderungen ihrer Arbeitsqualität unter GoA3 und ihrer Akzeptanz gegenüber GoA3 untersucht. Aktuell werden die erhobenen Daten ausgewertet, sodass bei der HF Summer School die Ergebnisse der Untersuchung und die daraus gewonnen Erkenntnisse besprochen werden sollen.

Energy-optimized headlamp distribution in urban areas

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Electric vehicles are becoming increasingly common on the roads, offering advantages in terms of sustainability and environmental impact. To maximize their driving range, manufacturers are seeking ways to reduce energy consumption. One significant area of energy use is vehicle lighting, particularly headlamp systems.

Headlamps primarily serve to enhance road users' safety at night by expanding the visual field of the driver and improving the detectability of other road users and potential hazards. In urban environments, street lighting should contribute to overall visibility. However, despite findings in several research papers, headlamps and streetlights are still developed independently, without mutual consideration of their combined lighting effects. This lack of coordination can lead to diminished visibility: overlapping light sources may reduce contrast, causing objects to blend into the background and making detection more difficult.

Based on these findings, previous approaches have proposed static headlamp distributions accounting for different levels of ambient light. However, these fail to adapt to the dynamic nature of urban driving conditions. This thesis aims to identify adaptive headlamp distributions that provide only as much light as necessary. The distributions dynamically change based on factors such as vehicle speed, ambient lighting, and the presence of other road users. Thereby, they should minimize energy use while maintaining safety.

Since subjective safety assessments vary across individuals and lack real-time applicability in a dynamic driving condition, objective methods will be

used. In an initial study, objective measurement methods will be validated. To this end, two contrasting light distributions - one very bright and one very dim - will be compared. The study will examine differences in driving performance, physiological responses, and eye movement behavior to determine whether reduced lighting leads to unsafe driving.

How sound properties affect preferred distances in human-drone interaction

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Drones are becoming increasingly commonplace in everyday life, be it delivery drones or surveillance drones. Previous research indicates that multiple factors shape how people perceive drones and interact with them. Here we focus on the role of engine noise on drone perception. We have applied an interactive interpersonal distance paradigm to assess the preferred closest distance to such drones. Sound is a necessary side-effect of drone operation, but it can be modified by the drone's technical design. In this study, we examined how acoustic properties, such as pitch and volume, as well as the size of the drone, influence the preferred distance to it. Participants experienced the drone in a virtual environment and adjusted its position to the closest comfortable distance. The study provides insights into how acoustic features affect preferred distance, which should be considered when designing drones.

When the Unexpected Occurs: The Influence of Human-Machine Interaction on User Reactions in Automated Vehicles

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The communication of transparency information through human-machine interfaces has been demonstrated to play a pivotal role in fostering vehicle users' trust in autonomous vehicles (Brandt et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024). While research suggests that increasing transparency levels lead to increasing levels of trust in automation (Brandt et al., 2024; Mercado et al., 2016), numerous studies illustrate that presenting an excessive amount of information in human-machine interfaces can overwhelm users (Basantis et al., 2021; Ha et al., 2020; Koo et al., 2015). Building on the work of Brandt et al. (2024) and Li et al. (2024), the objective of this thesis is to investigate which levels of the Situation Awareness-Based Agent Transparency (SAT) model of Chen et al. (2014) are required to establish vehicle users' trust while encountering unexpected situations during autonomous driving. An online study ($n = 126$) was conducted to examine the perceived likelihood, need for an explanation and preferred explanation (SAT 1, SAT 1 + 3, SAT 1 + 2 + 3) in nine vignettes describing rides with a highly automated rickshaw. Furthermore, 22 participants took part in a real-vehicle study using a within-subjects design to examine the effects of transparency (SAT 1 + 3, SAT 1 + 2 + 3) on trust (trust in automation, understanding/predictability) in three situations (baseline, GPS error, vandalized stop sign). The rides took place in an automated shuttle with a Wizard-of-Oz set up on a test field for automated vehicles (Margreiter et al., 2022). The results of the online study demonstrate that the preferred transparency information varies across traffic situations. However, there was

no significant effect of transparency on trust in the shuttle study. Overall, the studies emphasize the need for further research on the communication of transparency information during autonomous driving, particularly in real driving settings.

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